

IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN IMPROVING WORK ACTIVITY

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Abstract: The process of physical education is multifaceted. In this process, both education and upbringing are given. In the process of physical education, education will be focused on the formation and improvement of motor skills, abilities. At the same time, the physical development of the trainees is affected. The unity of all types of education, their interaction with each other is one of the fundamental pedagogical laws.

This article provides scientific information about the physical education system. The importance of physical education in the development of society has also been scientifically studied.

Keywords: sports, sports training, physical education, theory of physical education, principles of physical education, healthy lifestyle.

ВАЖНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ В УЛУЧШЕНИИ ТРУДОВОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ

Аннотация: Процесс физического воспитания многогранен. В этом процессе дается как образование, так и воспитание. В процессе физического воспитания образование будет направлено на формирование и совершенствование двигательных навыков, умений. В то же время это сказывается на физическом развитии обучаемых. Единство всех видов образования, их взаимодействие друг с другом является одним из основополагающих педагогических законов.

В этой статье представлена научная информация о системе физического воспитания. Важность физического воспитания в развитии общества также была научно изучена.

Ключевые Слова: спорт, спортивная подготовка, физическое воспитание, теория физического воспитания, принципы физического воспитания, здоровый образ жизни.

INTRODUCTION

Physical perfection is interpreted differently as a concept that has its own ideal classification for any historical period that changes historically, because this ideal reflects the economic conditions of the population, the worldview of social life. Physically fit is a historically formed perception of the norm of health and the level of comprehensive physical fitness, which optimally meets the requirements of longevity of labor, public, military and human creative activities.

Physical maturity has a clear meaning and social significance in the harmonious development of the individual. It has been proven in practice that activities performed only to achieve physical maturity lead to one-sidedness during the pedagogical process.

It should be implemented with the main directions of modernization of the system of physical education and improvement of physical fitness for young people in educational institutions, measures to improve the system of physical culture and sports for students, as well as recommendations to increase the effectiveness of compulsory physical education in education. To this end, the development of physical culture and sports in Uzbekistan is considered at the level of

state policy and is used as a guaranteed means of strengthening the nation's gene pool, educating a generation of physical and intellectual potential and promoting national independence.

Only when physical education is based on a clear system can a pre-determined result be achieved. The system of physical education means the generality of the principles, means, methods and forms of organization of physical education in such a way that it corresponds to the goals and objectives of the rich and all-round harmonious development of a member of society.

Physical education is a pedagogical process aimed at the morphological and functional improvement of the human body, the formation and improvement of basic motor skills, skills and knowledge related to them. It should be noted that the purpose of physical education in our country is to educate the people of Uzbekistan to be physically mature, active builders of the rule of law, ready for creative work and defense of the Motherland. "This goal is common to all organizations and institutions engaged in physical education in the country. The commonality of purpose is one of the basic laws of the system of physical education.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

The commonality of purpose is one of the basic laws of the physical education system. In response to these goals and conditions, in its implementation, the age, health, physical fitness, occupation of the trainees are taken into account, and specific tasks in physical education are solved:

- a) the harmonious development of the form function of the human body, the full development of physical abilities, the strengthening of health and the orientation of a member of society to longevity;
- b) formation of vital movement skills and abilities, special knowledge of physical culture, which is necessary in everyday life;
- c) training of physical qualities for all-round physical development;

The level of development of physical culture in society is assessed by the following indicators:

- the degree to which members of society incorporate physical culture into their daily lives;
- health and physical fitness of members of society;
- Material and technical support of physical culture classes and their quality;
- with a permanent staff (staff), qualifications and activity and ability of the staff in charge of physical culture;
- evaluated by the results of community members in sports.

The independence of our country, the ongoing social and economic reforms in our society demand that the children of our country must have reached physical maturity. Every nation is proud of its heroes, their physically fit sons. They dreamed that their children would be physically and spiritually formed, such as Alpomish, Rustam, Gorogly, Barchinoy in folklore.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The fact that the purpose and task of physical education is related to other educational processes is understood in such a way that this compatibility is of an objective nature and gives a legitimate direction to the process of physical education. In the process of physical education, as in other areas of education, goal-oriented activities have been shown to not always meet the planned outcome. In physical education, the results of training for a young athlete or physiotherapist need to take into account the impact of planned exercise on his body. does not justify. This impedes all-round harmonious development and undermines sporting achievements.

Therefore, in front of the educator and the coach, the need to be able to see far, to make predictions will be cross-cutting. The solution of this task should be carried out in the system of training educated, knowledgeable and loving professionals. Our young, newly recognized country, through various categories of state and non-state sports societies, associations of physical culture enthusiasts, is focusing on the creation of a single system of physical education, combining spiritual wealth, physical perfection, nationalism and its scientific features.

From time immemorial, Eastern thinkers have paid special attention to the issue of a spiritually rich, physically fit and perfect man. It is said that the greatest of the qualities of perfection is the perfection of the human body. Only a healthy body has the positive qualities of a person, such as perseverance, piety, piety, contentment, knowledge, patience, discipline, self, conscience, truthfulness, vision, example, chastity, modesty, understanding, intelligence, economy, obedience, forgiveness, love of country. considered to be achieved through familiarity.

The popularization of the physical culture system of our country means that we have the opportunity to engage the peoples of our multinational republic in the form of national games with "popular sports", which are included in the program of physical exercises, national sports, mass sports, Olympics.

CONCLUSION

In short, the generality of the theoretical, methodological practice of the process of physical education is the basis of the system of physical education. The study of the heritage of our nation in this area is the main task of our science. We are convinced that the physical culture of the peoples and nations of our country, which gave birth to the Jahangirs, has taken its place in historical sources.

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